

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART XI

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For pharmacological study against amoebiasis, 2-methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsonic acid and 2-methylquinoline-6-arsonic acid have been synthesised.

The pronounced antiseptic property of chiniofon (sodium salt of 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid) and of chinosol (8-hydroxyquinoline sulphate) is well known, the former drug being often used, with success, in the form of retention enema in chronic cases of amoebic dysentery. So far as the sulphonic acid group in chiniofon is concerned, it is difficult to arrive at the precise function of this group in relation to the pharmacological action of the compound. But the pronounced antiseptic property of chinnosol and vioform—compounds which are structurally allied to chiniofon but do not contain any sulphonic acid group—indicates that the function of the sulphonic acid group in chiniofon might be purely physical in that it confers solubility in aqueous medium to the sodium derivative of the compound.

The pronounced amoebicidal property of carbarsone or stovarsol indicates that it will be worth while to search for an ideal amoebicide in substituted phenylarsonic acid derivatives. In view of the above observations it has been considered to be of interest to synthesise 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsonic acid, the iodo derivative of which will be structurally related to chiniofon.

Some quinoline-arsonic acids are known in literature and they have been prepared by diazotising the corresponding aminoquinolines and treating the solution with sodium arsenite in the usual way. The arsonic acids are not obtained directly from the reaction mixture but are reduced to the arseno compounds, which are subsequently oxidised with hydrogen peroxide to yield the acids. This method is tedious and generally gives poor yields. It has been, therefore, considered desirable to explore other methods for the synthesis of quinoline-arsonic acids. Döbner and Miller (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 2812) discovered that paraldehyde heated with aniline and concentrated hydrochloric acid gave quinaldine. The mechanism of this reaction was first satisfactorily explained by Beyer (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1886, 33, 423), who suggested that crotonaldehyde, produced from two molecules of paraldehyde, formed an additive product with aniline, ring-closure then proceeding as in the Skraup reaction (*cf.* Blaise and Maire, *Compt. rend.*, 1907, 144, 93). Later work showed that this method of Döbner and Miller is of general applicability and that practically any aromatic amine may be condensed with an unsaturated aldehyde to give substituted quinolines.

Following the method of Döbner and Miller, 2-methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsonic acid (I) has now been synthesised by the interaction of 3-amino-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid and paraldehyde. The compound (I) yields the

7-iodo derivative. Similarly, by reacting *p*-arsanic acid with paraldehyde under identical conditions, 2-methylquinoline-6-arsonic acid has now been obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsonic Acid (I).—3-Amino-2-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid (23 g.) was treated with commercial concentrated hydrochloric acid (19 c.c.). The hydrochloride, which was precipitated, was thoroughly triturated and to this mixture paraldehyde (freshly distilled, 14 c.c.) was added dropwise under shaking. Slight heat was generated and the hydrochloride gradually went into solution. The solution was allowed to stand for 1 hour and then heated under reflux in an oil-bath at 100–105° for 2 hours and then at 120–125° for 3 hours, and finally allowed to stand overnight.

Next day the solution was diluted with water, filtered and carefully neutralised, under cooling, with cold 10% sodium hydroxide solution, when a brown solid was precipitated. This was filtered, washed with water and then boiled with water 2–3 times till the filtrate became colourless. The solid is practically insoluble in almost all organic solvents and water, and was purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and neutralising with cold 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The brownish solid was finally washed with hot alcohol and then with ether, yield 8 g. It is readily soluble in alkali carbonates and in mineral acids and does not melt even at 300°. (Found : As, 25.82 ; N, 4.49. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4NA_s$ requires As, 26.50 ; N, 4.94 per cent). It does not contain any diazotisable amino group. A dilute hydrochloric acid solution of the compound gives immediately a brown precipitate with Mayer's reagent, a pale brown precipitate with potassium dichromate solution, and a pink colouration (gradually developed on standing) with ferric chloride solution.

7-Iodo-2-methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsonic Acid.—A cold alcoholic solution of iodine monochloride (prepared from 2g. of iodine) was slowly added, under stirring, to a solution of the above compound (I, 4g.) dissolved in water (80 c.c.) containing sodium bicarbonate (1.2 g). Immediately the iodo derivative was precipitated, which was allowed to stand for 1 hour with occasional shaking. It was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It was next triturated with excess of 1% aqueous sodium bisulphite solution, filtered, washed with water, and then again triturated with excess of 2% sodium thiosulphate solution, filtered and washed thoroughly with water and then with alcohol. The deep brown solid, thus obtained, is practically insoluble in almost all organic solvents and does not melt even at 300°. (Found : I, 30.28. $C_{10}H_9O_4NA_sI$ requires I, 31.05

per cent). When heated with concentrated sulphuric acid, copious vapour of iodine is evolved. When a dilute nitric acid solution of this compound is shaken with chloroform, the chloroform layer turns violet, the colour deepening on standing.

2-Methylquinoline-6-arsonic Acid (II).—Commercial concentrated hydrochloric acid (56 c.c.) was poured dropwise into a flask containing well powdered *p*-arsanilic acid (63g.), when the hydrochloride of *p*-arsanilic acid was formed. To this mixture was added dropwise paraldehyde (freshly distilled, 46 c.c.) under stirring, when there was slight rise in temperature and the hydrochloride gradually went into solution. The solution was then refluxed in an oil-bath for 3 hours at 120-25° and then allowed to stand overnight.

Next day the solution was diluted with water, and carefully neutralised under cooling, with cold 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution, when a brown solid was precipitated, which was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It is practically insoluble in almost all organic solvents. It was triturated and washed with alcohol and then with ether, yield 15g. The brownish solid does not melt even at 300° and is readily soluble in alkali carbonates and in mineral acids. (Found : N, 4.94 ; As, 28.61. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3NA_3$ requires N, 5.24 ; As, 28.09 per cent).

The compound does not contain any diazotisable amino group. A dilute hydrochloric acid solution of the above compound gives a brown precipitate with Mayer's reagent, a pale brown precipitate with potassium dichromate solution and an insoluble zinc salt with a solution of zinc chloride in dilute hydrochloric acid.

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Received September 11, 1945.

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